

THE EMERGENCE AND DEVELOPMENT OF MILITARY DOCTRINAL RULES

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Annotation. This article analyzes the emergence, development of military-doctrinal rules and their role in the state national security system based on a systematic and dialectical approach. The article scientifically substantiates the normative (directive) and informational (foreign policy) functions of the doctrine, as well as the laws of interaction between its stable political and dynamic military-strategic aspects in the context of modern hybrid and local conflicts.

Keywords. Military doctrine, methodology, political basis, economic potential, legal basis, normative function, information function, military-strategic aspect, dialectical relationship, security dilemma.

Today, when the nature of military threats is changing and the boundaries between war and peace are blurring, scientific research into military doctrines, which are the programmatic framework of state defense policy, is of great importance. Military doctrine is not just a declarative document, but a system of firm views aimed at solving the scientific problems of the state in the military sphere. This article systematically analyzes the factors of formation of military doctrines, their functional structure, and the dialectical relationship between political views and military-technical capabilities.

Military threats occupy a key place among the scientific problems of the military sphere that have arisen today, the tasks of ensuring the country's defense. They are traditionally considered the subject of military doctrine and regulate aspects of the state's internal relations in the field of strengthening national security.

Doctrine is derived from the Latin word *Doctrina* (teaching, science, study, education), and means a philosophical, political, religious concept, theory, teaching, system of views, instructions of theoretical and political principles.

Military doctrine in the classical sense is an expression of the views adopted in the state on the political assessment of the future war, the state's attitude to war, determining the nature of the future war, the country's economic and moral readiness for war, the construction and training of the armed forces, and the methods of waging war.

Military doctrine is directly related to the social structure of the country, state-wide tasks in the field of domestic and foreign policy, its economic, political-moral and cultural situation, and its specific national characteristics.

Military doctrine uses the conclusions of various sciences. In particular, the doctrine relies on the conclusions of military science in determining the nature of the future war, the methods of waging it, the construction and training of the Armed Forces.

Based on this, when developing a military doctrine, it is advisable to rely on a certain methodology that allows you to substantiate and determine its content and essence, components, interdependence, and development processes. This takes into account the

processes taking place in the world and in the country, the geostrategic and socio-economic situation of the state, and a deep and comprehensive analysis of political, economic, legal, scientific, and other factors of an objective and subjective nature.

The conclusions drawn from the above factors serve as the basis for the formation of military-doctrinal views. They allow you to substantiate and determine the tasks of ensuring national security, as well as the political, economic, and legal basis of the military doctrine.

The political foundations usually include: the general political goals of the state and the goals of domestic and foreign policy arising from them; the state's attitude to war as a means of achieving political goals and the place occupied by the armed forces in the political organization of society. All this is reflected in the state constitution, laws, resolutions, decrees and other official documents.

The economic foundations of the military doctrine are the achieved level of development of the economy, its ability to provide the state's defense needs at a high level of quality; the number and qualitative composition of the population, other material and scientific and technical capabilities of the country. Economic foundations express the state's ability to use a certain part of its economic potential for defense needs.

The legal foundations of the military doctrine are the political and military goals of the state, enshrined in law, the main directions of military construction, the rights and obligations of state institutions and military officials of the country in the field of defense. They are stipulated in the constitution, the concept of national (state) security and other legal acts on military policy.

With a gradual or sharp change in the foundations of the military doctrine, its provisions may conflict with reality or develop and improve. In this case, it is inevitable that it will be supplemented with new provisions.

The adopted provisions of the military doctrine determine the main directions for conducting research for military science and military strategy.

The military doctrine of any state performs two functions, namely normative and informational.

The first, namely normative, function is to require strict adherence and implementation by certain state bodies responsible for the security of the country, since almost all provisions of the military doctrine have a directive nature.

The normative function of the military doctrine is to serve as the basis for using its provisions as initial data in planning the construction, training and use of the armed forces in a possible war.

The second function is informative. This function is to convey to the population of the country, personnel of the armed forces the tasks of the state in the field of military policy, strengthening its defense capabilities, maintaining an adequate level of combat readiness of the army. This function of the military doctrine also has foreign policy aspects, which are to convey to the world community the essence of the country's military policy and defense construction.

The military doctrine of the state should answer the following main questions in content: the state's attitude to the problems of war and peace, whether it considers war to be an acceptable way to resolve conflicts or not;

by what means and methods to solve the problems of preventing war, ensuring the country's security and strengthening its defense capabilities;

What is the source of military danger, what is the level of direct military threat, what kind of enemy will be fought in a possible war and who can be allies in it;

What will be the form and characteristics of the war in which the state and its armed forces may participate;

What political and strategic goals and tasks may be set before them in such a war;

What should be the armed forces to fulfill the assigned tasks, in what direction should their construction be carried out;

How should the country prepare for a possible war be carried out;

What methods and forms of military operations should be used to wage the war.

The content of military doctrine is made up of its political and military-strategic aspects.

The political aspect of military doctrine is the main one. It determines the state's attitude to war and the use of force, the national interests of the state and factors influencing it, that is, the nature of the military danger, its scale, sources and probability of a military threat, the probability of war and methods of its prevention, the forces and means necessary for this, military-political goals in war, possible enemies and allies.

In the political aspect of the doctrine, the main attention is paid to ensuring the security of the state from external military threats. The range of methods chosen for this is wide. Among the main ones are, if war cannot be prevented, the method of containing the aggressor and armed protection of the state's sovereignty and territorial integrity.

The development of state policy, including defense policy, usually begins with determining national interests. This problem is quite complex. It can be noted that even states with established views and traditions do not always have a developed system of national interests.

In a broad sense, national interests can be considered the most important vital interests that ensure the development of the state in all areas of its activities within the world community.

In summary, national interests must be reflected in the constitution, and their expanded interpretation in the concept of national security.

When determining the causes and sources of a military threat, it is necessary to assess the following factors. First, the presence of serious contradictions, including territorial claims, contradictions of an economic, national-ethnic and religious nature, as well as aspirations to interfere in internal affairs. Second, the presence of large military potential and a grouping of armed forces that are sufficiently powerful in peacetime by the opposing states. Third, the practical demonstration by this state of the use of force to achieve political goals.

In the current conditions, political means should remain the priority in preventing war. They will be effective only if they are based on a sufficient level of economic and military power of the state.

The political goals and tasks of the state and its armed forces in war are to protect its sovereignty, territorial integrity and other important vital interests.

A special place in the structural structure of the military doctrine can be allocated to the system of views on collective security and the prevention of possible aggression by political, economic and, in particular, military means.

Based on the fundamental political guidelines, the military-strategic aspect of the military doctrine includes the problems of military construction and its basis - the formation of armed

forces, the forms and methods of repelling aggression and conducting hostilities, and the preparation of troops (forces) for war.

It defines: the strategic nature of a possible war; the strategic goals and tasks that the armed forces may face; what armed forces are needed for the state, the main directions of their construction, provision with weapons and military equipment, and other issues, including military cooperation; the methods and forms of using armed forces, as well as the requirements for preparing the population, economy, and territory of the country for a possible war.

Determining the strategic nature of a possible war in order to develop a guideline for what kind of war it is necessary to prepare for is an important provision of the military-strategic aspect of the doctrine.

As is known, previously, the main attention in the military doctrine was paid to the provisions on nuclear world and large-scale conventional wars. Insufficient attention was paid to local wars and armed conflicts. However, the probability of such wars and conflicts is high, although the possibility of a large-scale, including a world war, is not excluded. In the current conditions, the armed forces of the state must be ready for military operations of any nature and scale and be able to conduct them.

The political and military-strategic aspects of military doctrine are dialectically closely interconnected and are classified by the following main aspects.

First, they are inseparable from each other, being considered components of a single whole, a set of views called military doctrine. Just as war cannot be separated from politics, content from form, and event from essence, the military-technical aspect of military doctrine cannot be separated from politics. Without taking into account the goals and directions of state policy, it is impossible to correctly resolve any issue of the country's readiness for war or correctly assign tasks to the armed forces.

Secondly, the political aspect of the military doctrine is classified by its stability. This is determined by the fact that the fundamental political provisions of the military doctrine are determined by the relatively stable social structure of the state and the nature of the policy it pursues.

This does not mean that clarifications cannot be made to the political aspect of the doctrine, if the time comes, significant changes can be made to a single social structure. But this does not apply to the fundamental foundations of the state's attitude to the problems of war and peace. Changes are determined by the military-political situation that has arisen and the tasks set for the state and the armed forces at a particular stage of historical development arising from it.

The military-strategic aspect of the doctrine is more dynamic and changes more often than politically, since the doctrine is influenced not only by serious changes in the political content, but also by the state of the economy and its ability to provide the armed forces with material and technical means, the emergence of new weapons and military equipment, the combat and moral-political (psychological) state of the army, and other similar factors.

Thirdly, both aspects of military doctrine influence each other. Politics, in addition to directly influencing military affairs, also influences the economy, which is the material basis of war, and people, through their moral state. In turn, the influence of the military-strategic aspect of military doctrine on the political aspect expresses the political goals of war in peacetime by

comparing the military capabilities of the state and, in particular, the combat potential of the armed forces.

In conclusion, it can be said that when developing the state's Defense Doctrine, it is advisable to rely on a certain methodology that allows us to substantiate and determine its content and essence, components (military-political, military-strategic and military-economic aspects), interdependence, and development processes, based on generally recognized principles.

List of used literature:

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